

Analysis and Experiment of Effective Rake Angle on the Cutting Forces and Chip Formation in Negative Inserts

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ABSTRACT

This report talks about how understanding how things are cut, and chips are made is important for making stuff efficiently. It explains the basics of how cutting forces are created, like the shape of the tool and how fast it's cutting, and how the material affects this. It also talks about how the chips that are made during cutting affect the quality of the surface, how long the tool lasts, and how much energy is used. Then, it explains how computers can help us simulate these forces and the shape of the chips. There are different ways to do this. Each way helps us understand how everything works together. By doing this, we can make the manufacturing process better, design better tools, and predict when tools might need fixing. The report also mentions that this kind of work involves different fields like engineering, materials science, and FEA in computers. It talks about new ways of simulating things, like including how heat affects the process and how materials change shape. Even though there are still challenges, like making sure the computer models are accurate and fast enough, the report says we should keep using these simulations in manufacturing. They help us make things better, use fewer resources, and be more competitive. By using computer tools and working together, we can find new ways to improve manufacturing.

Keywords: Cutting Forces, Negative Insert, Milling Inserts, Chip Formation, Rake Angle, Tool Life.

1. Introduction

Milling machining stands as a cornerstone in modern manufacturing processes, facilitating the production of intricate components across diverse industries [1]. At the heart of milling lies the intricate interplay of cutting parameters, with the rake angle of cutting inserts emerging as a crucial determinant of machining efficiency and quality [2]. Within this realm, negative inserts, commonly employed in milling operations, underscore the significance of rake angle in shaping cutting forces and chip formation dynamics. The rake angle, representing the angle between the cutting edge and the work piece surface, stands as a pivotal parameter dictating tool engagement and chip flow direction [3]. Consequently, delving into the nuanced relationship between rake angle, cutting forces, and chip formation assumes paramount importance for optimizing milling processes. This study embarks on a comprehensive exploration, blending analysis and experimentation, to unravel the intricate influence of rake angle variations on cutting forces and chip formation characteristics in negative inserts during milling operations [4]. Through a systematic examination of these factors, this research endeavors to illuminate pathways for refining machining strategies and tailoring tool geometries to elevate milling performance across industries [5].

Machining operations, particularly milling, demand meticulous attention to cutting parameters to ensure optimal outcomes. Among these parameters, the rake angle emerges as a fundamental factor exerting profound influence on machining dynamics [6]. Defined as the angle between the cutting edge and the work piece surface, the rake angle embodies a pivotal role in shaping the

interaction between the cutting tool and the work piece material. In the realm of negative inserts, where the geometry is configured to promote a downward chip flow, the significance of rake angle amplifies. Variations in rake angle dictate the extent of tool engagement and the trajectory of chip formation, thereby influencing cutting forces and chip morphology [7]. Understanding these intricate dynamics is indispensable for fine-tuning milling processes to achieve superior efficiency, surface finish, and tool longevity [8].

The influence of rake angle on cutting forces constitutes a focal point of interest in machining research [9]. Cutting forces, comprising axial, radial, and tangential components, encapsulate the energy expended during material removal [10]. The rake angle serves as a critical determinant of these forces, with variations eliciting distinct responses in cutting force magnitudes and directions. In negative inserts, altering the rake angle can modulate the degree of chip compression, thereby influencing the distribution of cutting forces along the tool-work piece interface [11].

Moreover, the morphology of chips generated during milling operations reflects the intricate interplay of cutting parameters, with rake angle assuming a central role [12]. Chip formation dynamics are intricately intertwined with rake angle variations, manifesting in alterations to chip shape, thickness, and segmentation [13]. Negative inserts, characterized by their ability to produce short, segmented chips conducive to efficient evacuation, underscore the importance of rake angle in shaping chip morphology [14]. The rake angle governs the direction of chip flow and the extent of chip segmentation, thereby influencing chip disposal mechanisms and mitigating chip recutting. Consequently, exploring the impact of rake angle on chip formation holds promise for refining chip evacuation strategies, reducing chip-tool interactions, and enhancing machining efficiency [15].

In light of these considerations, this study embarks on a multifaceted exploration, blending theoretical analysis with practical experimentation, to unravel the intricate nexus between rake angle, cutting forces, and chip formation in negative inserts during milling operations [16]. By systematically varying rake angle parameters and meticulously monitoring cutting forces and chip morphology characteristics, this research seeks to discern underlying trends, elucidate causal relationships, and extract actionable insights for machining optimization [17]. Through a judicious synthesis of empirical findings and theoretical frameworks, this study endeavors to pave the way for informed decision-making in tool design, process planning, and machining operations, fostering a paradigm shift towards enhanced efficiency, quality, and sustainability in milling machining [18].

2. Material and method

2.1 Experimental equipment

Kistler Dynamometer accurately measures forces, pressures, and acceleration, aiding in understanding interactions in various fields like automotive engineering and sports science for safety and performance optimization. The sensor functions like a specialized measuring spoon, detecting force, pressure, or acceleration with precision. The amplifier enhances these measurements, akin to a magnifying glass, while the data acquisition system organizes and stores the data systematically, resembling a recipe book for easy reference.

The MITUTOYO Portable Surface Roughness Tester is a convenient tool for assessing surface texture on the go, ensuring quality in industries such as automotive and aerospace with its user-friendly design. The material properties of steel 4140 are given in Table 1.

Table 1: RAW Material – STEEL. 4140 Properties of experimental samples

SL No	Mechanical Properties	Value
1	Tensile Strength	850 MPa
2	Yield Strength	655 MPa
3	Hardness	28 Brinell
4	Poisson's Ratio	0.29
5	Thermal Conductivity	44.5 W/mK
6	Specific Heat Capacity	0.46 J/kgK
7	Melting Point	1416 °C
8	Density	7850 g/cm ³

2.2 Experimental samples

During the cutting cycle, the engagement of the cutter with the workpiece results in varying forces and chip thickness reduce significantly. The angle of the cutting tool also influences chip formation, affecting the ease of chip removal and preventing process disruption. Optimal angles produce shorter chips, aiding in smooth cutting and preventing overheating that could damage the tool. thicknesses. Initially, there's higher force and thicker chips, which gradually decrease towards the middle of the cycle.

2.3 Machine tool, cutting tool and cutting [parameters]

In milling operations that utilize carbide inserts, a series of crucial processes are employed to ensure efficient machining. One such process is chip breaking, which is vital for preventing the formation of long, continuous chips that could potentially damage the cutting tool and compromise the quality of the surface finish [19]. Techniques such as implementing specialized chip breakers on inserts or adjusting cutting parameters like feed rate and depth of cut are commonly employed to achieve effective chip breaking. Another important aspect of milling operations with carbide inserts is tool life testing [20]. This process involves evaluating the durability and performance of the carbide inserts under specific cutting conditions. By conducting tool life testing, machinists can determine the optimal cutting parameters and tool geometries that maximize tool longevity and productivity while maintaining the desired surface finish standards.

2.4 Cutting Parameters

In addition to tool life testing, force testing is also carried out during milling operations. Force testing involves measuring the cutting forces experienced by the tool during machining. This data is instrumental in optimizing cutting parameters, tool selection, and machining strategies to minimize tool wear, energy consumption, and the risk of work piece deformation. Furthermore, achieving the desired surface finish is a primary objective in milling operations using carbide inserts. Carbide inserts, renowned for their superior hardness and wear resistance, contribute significantly to maintaining consistent surface quality over prolonged periods. To achieve the desired surface finish, machinists carefully regulate cutting parameters such as

cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut. Additionally, proper tool geometry and coolant application play essential roles in ensuring the quality of the surface finish [21]. Overall, these processes—chip breaking, tool life testing, force testing, and surface finish optimization—are integral components of milling operations utilizing carbide inserts. They collectively contribute to efficient material removal, prolonged tool longevity, and the attainment of high-quality surface finishes, thereby enhancing the overall productivity and quality of machining operations [22].

2.5 Process Parameters

Table 2: Process Parameters Table

Process Parameters	Low	Mid	High
Cutting Speed (V_c) m/min	200	235	250
Feed/tooth in mm	0.15	0.18	0.2
A_p (DOC) in mm	1.5	2	2.5
A_e (Radial Engagment) in mm	50	50	50

3. Results and Discussion

Main cutting force results were obtained with three different types of depth of cut (1.5mm, 2 mm, 2.5mm), feed rate (0.15 mm/rev, 0.18mm/rev, 0.2mm/rev), three different cutting speeds (200, 235 and 250 m/min) Based on values listed in Table 3, main cutting force values for three cutting speeds for different rake angles were given in separately.

Figure. 1. HIGH Parameter Surface finish and Force graphs

In Table 3, the most significant finding was that as the rake angle of the tool increased in the positive direction, the main cutting force decreased, regardless of the cutting speed. Conversely, when the rake angle was increased in the opposite direction, the cutting force increased. This is because changing the rake angle affects the contact area the equipment and enhances its longevity and performance. By minimizing Z-axis cutting force, proper tool angles help prevent shaky cutting, ensuring stability and smooth operation throughout the machining process. Ultimately, choosing the correct tool angle not only extends tool life but also improves

machining efficiency and quality, minimizing costs and downtime associated with tool replacement and process disruptions.

Table 3: Force, Power, and Surface finish values

SL No	Forces	Cutting Speed, (Vc) = 200 (m/min)	Cutting Speed, (Vc) = 235 (m/min)	Cutting Speed, (Vc) = 250 (m/min)
1	Fx	276.5	416.6	507.8
2	Fy	667.1	990.4	1303
3	Fz	35.16	43.21	77.64

between the tool and the chip. Previous studies have also shown similar results, indicating that increasing the rake angle positively influences cutting forces. This is because it reduces the contact area between the tool and the chip, resulting in less friction and easier chip flow. The results from this study confirmed that changing the rake angle in the positive direction led to a decrease in cutting force. Additionally, the cutting speed had a minor effect on the cutting force compared to the rake angle. The most significant decrease in cutting force was observed at cutting speeds of 200, 235, and 250 m/min when the rake angle ranged. A smaller decrease was noted at a cutting speed of 250 m/min with the same rake angle. However, the most substantial reduction in cutting forces occurred at a cutting speed, when the rake angle changed.

Figure 2. FORCE VS TIME Graphs

4. Conclusion

The angle of the cutting tool plays a crucial role in achieving desired surface finishes. By selecting the appropriate angle, we can control how chips are formed, preventing issues like built-up edge and ensuring a smooth surface finish. Additionally, a higher angle makes cutting easier, reducing the force required and minimizing the risk of leaving marks or causing vibrations that could compromise the surface quality. Furthermore, the angle of the tool influences chip flow and removal during cutting operations. Optimal angles help produce shorter chips that are easier to remove, promoting a smoother cutting process and preventing the tool from overheating, which could lead to damage. Choosing the right tool angle is particularly important when working with less powerful machines.

By selecting the correct angle, we can reduce stress on the machine, improving its performance and longevity. This ensures that the machine operates efficiently without being overworked, ultimately extending its lifespan and enhancing its effectiveness. Moreover, the angle of the tool directly impacts tool lifespan. Selecting the right angle helps prevent premature wear and tear on the tool, as less force is required for cutting, reducing the rate of tool degradation. Conversely, choosing the wrong angle can accelerate tool wear, necessitating frequent replacements, which incur additional costs and downtime. Additionally, optimizing the tool angle helps minimize Z-axis cutting force, reducing the likelihood of shaky cutting. By keeping everything stable and smooth, the cutting process can proceed seamlessly without the risk of vibrations or instability that could disrupt the machining operation. Selecting the appropriate tool angle is crucial for achieving smooth surface finishes, efficient chip flow and removal, prolonging tool lifespan, minimizing stress on machines, and preventing shaky cutting. This careful consideration of tool angles contributes to overall machining success, cost-effectiveness, and productivity.

5. References

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